

D4.1

Evolutionary Infrastructure

Inventory

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Report Nr 1

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
BMP	Bonseyes Marketplace
VLabs	Virtual research labs
VoCE	Virtual Center-of-excellence
LPDNN	Low Power Deep Neural Network (Bonseyes software library to compresses AI models for a given target platform).
DPE	Bonseyes Developer Platform Environments
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
NIS2	The NIS2 Directive is the EU-wide legislation on cybersecurity. It provides legal measures to boost the overall level of cybersecurity in the EU.
DIH	Digital Innovation Hubs
SoC	System-on-Chips
MPSoC	Multiprocessor systems-on-chips

Executive Summary

This first version of the Evolutive Infrastructure Inventory (Report Nr 1, Deliverable D4.1) provides a current inventory of edge AI resources, objects, artefacts, and concepts available in the dAIEDGE consortium. In the future, these resources will be made accessible by dAIEDGE's "virtual center-of-excellence" and its virtual research labs (VLabs). These facilities aim at accelerating and deepening European research in highly distributed edge AI systems.

As a first gap analysis, the current inventory reveals a large diversity of edge AI hardware and software resources available within the consortium. These resources comprise more than 20 kinds of software objects and about 10-15 hardware types. While a satisfying response ratio was achieved (66%), certain larger hardware and software partners in dAIEDGE have not yet been able to classify their resources and provide input to the inventory. A hypothesis for this is the complexity within these partners for conducting such an inventory survey at these partners, including many contact points in the partners and legal issues such as licenses. Our aim is to improve the coverage of the inventory and provide the partners with dedicated support.

The deliverable D4.1 comprises two parts: first, a short document is describing the inventory as it is currently seen, the chosen categories of edge AI objects, and the methods and processes to acquire the data for the inventory. The second part is a database of the inventory and is implemented by an Excel file. The M06 version of the inventory is available as an Excel File ("Evolutive_Infrastructure_Inventory_M06.xlsx") upon request.

The classification of the inventory is based on an expected three-layer structure of the "virtual center-of-excellence" and the VLabs. These three layers are:

- an inner core of "edge AI services and objects, e.g. edge AI models, data sets, computational facilities, or edge AI hardware,
- a middle layer of "Management and Operational Services, e.g. authentication and authorization mechanisms or concepts for enforcing societal compliance, and
- an outer layer of "community building services", e.g. AI marketplaces, software repositories or directories, or testbed federations.

Besides describing the classification, this document:

- details the methods used to acquire the data, i.e., the design of the applied questionnaire and the support to the consortium for answering it, e.g., to verify the validity of the data,
- provides statistics on available resources, e.g., to permit gap analysis and strategy development for the VLab design,
- points to the catalog of resources, i.e., the Excel database, which allows for searching for edge AI resources; thus enabling technical solutions for sharing and integration into a VLab,
- and a lists of contact points at dAIEDGE partners for continuous information collection and fast updates of the inventory as well as for a rapid verification of requirements and technical details.
- provide very first statistics and gap analysis.

This version (Report Nr 1) of the Evolutive Infrastructure Inventory (Deliverable D4.1) supports the internal communication and development activities in the dAIEDGE Network-of-Excellence project and is part of the milestone MS1 at month 06 (M06).

A refined and evolved version of the Evolutive Infrastructure Inventory (Report Nr 2, Deliverable D4.6, M12) will be available in month 12 and as part of milestone MS2. The more detailed version (D4.6) aims at a deeper and more comprehensive description of the requirements, identification of the gaps in resources (Objective O4.1), challenges and capabilities, and internal road mapping of the project for the VLabs.

The deliverable provides input data for task T4.2 (“Virtual research lab design” [M06-M12]), which will perform the actual design and technical implementation of the VLabs.

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1. Introduction

The rapidly evolving landscape of edge AI systems presents both opportunities and challenges for researchers and practitioners alike. As part of the dAIEDGE consortium's ongoing efforts to advance the field of highly distributed edge AI, this first version of the Evolutive Infrastructure Inventory (Report Nr 1, Deliverable D4.1) offers the initial step towards a comprehensive inventory of edge AI resources, objects, artefacts, and concepts available within the consortium. Through the establishment of a virtual center-of-excellence (VoCE) and virtual research labs (VLabs), dAIEDGE aims to democratize access to these resources and accelerate European research in this promising field, cf. dAIEDGE description of work.

Through this deliverable, we begin working on the foundation for collaborative research, innovation, and knowledge sharing in highly distributed edge AI systems. By harnessing the collective expertise and resources within this excellent consortium, dAIEDGE aims to drive transformative advancements in edge AI research and applications, ultimately shaping the future of European digital innovation.

In order to get an initial overview of the inventory, we conducted a survey to collect information from all the participating partners of the dAIEDGE consortium. Our method to design the questionnaire was motivated by a clustered approach that consists of three layers. As illustrated in Figure 1, the classification of the inventory is structured around these three layers since we envisioned such an architecture for the envisioned VoCE and VLabs: an inner core of edge AI services and objects, a middle layer of management and operational services, and an outer layer of community-building services. This framework not only guides the organization of the inventory but also informs strategy development for the design and implementation of VLabs.

In addition to detailing the classification methodology and data acquisition processes, this document offers insights into available resources, statistical analysis, and gap identification. It also provides a roadmap for leveraging the Excel database for resource discovery, integration, and collaboration within the consortium. Contact points at dAIEDGE partners are included to facilitate ongoing information exchange, updates to the inventory, and verification of technical requirements. Furthermore, this document serves as a preliminary gap analysis, revealing a diverse array of edge AI hardware and software resources within the consortium. It also tries to shed light on the challenges faced by several partners regarding identification of shareable artifacts and their corresponding classification. Thus, room for renewed effort and exploration towards further collaboration and data collection can be observed. Deliverable D4.1 is divided into two parts: a descriptive document outlining the inventory's categories, acquisition methods, and statistical analysis, and an accompanying Excel database providing a detailed catalog of resources.

The rest of this document is organized as follows: Section 2 elaborates on the technical vision, aims, objectives and challenges associated with this endeavor. Section 3 discusses the methods and technologies used within the scope of this deliverable. The results and gap analysis are presented in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 concludes this deliverable with an outlook towards the next phases.

2. Technical Vision, Aims and Objectives

In this section, we discuss the Technical Vision, Aims, and Objectives as well as challenges of the Virtual Center of Excellence (VCoE), a transformative initiative poised to drive innovation, collaboration, and excellence in the edge AI ecosystem. In order to cater for today's as well as tomorrow's requirements, the Technical Vision outlines the overarching principles and guiding framework that will underpin the development and operation of the VCoE. Our Aims and Objectives include the strategic goals and milestones we aim to achieve through the establishment of this cutting-edge platform. We envision a comprehensive as well as evolutive inventory for the VCoE's creation and evolution. This section sets the stage for a dynamic and impactful journey towards fostering synergy, knowledge-sharing, and advancement within the European edge AI landscape.

2.1. Vision of a Virtual Center-of-Excellence

dAIEDGE aims at building a virtual center of excellence. Its target is to accelerate Europe's edge AI research as well as providing an environment for expedited development of technologies and business opportunities around edge AI technologies, systems, and applications. The virtual center will be also a place for tangible and strong technical collaborations with relevant stakeholders in research and industry, also including rapid movers such as Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH), AI start-up initiatives, incubators, and international industrial and scientific clusters.

Objective 5 will be addressed by designing a framework for edge AI resource integration and by building one or more virtual laboratory environments (VLabs). The VLabs will be characterized by high usability, simple accessibility, and appropriate security, compliance and incentivization mechanisms.

The framework and the VLabs will integrate the cutting-edge edge AI technologies and resources available in the consortium. They can be used for advanced research activities as well as for developing new ways of testing and commercializing edge AI applications. They will provide resources to all consortium partners and eventually beyond. Furthermore, the labs will also provide for community building.

dAIEDGE 's interpretation of the vision for a framework can be visualized by a three-layer onion model, cf. Figure 1. It outlines some of the layers' functions and relationships at each level of the hierarchy.

Figure 1: dAIedge AI-as-a-Service vision

2.2. Aims, Objectives, and Challenges

The primary aim and objective of this initial effort regarding building an evolutive inventory is to offer a foundation for the envisioned Virtual Center of Excellence (VCoE) and Virtual Lab (VLab). These are aligned with the overarching goal of the Network of Excellence (NoE) --- accelerating and deepening European research in highly distributed edge AI systems. Through the establishment of technical but virtual facilities, the goal is to catalyze innovation and collaboration within the European research community, creating a dynamic ecosystem for the advancement of cutting-edge technologies. Then we also aim to provide an accessible platform that facilitates knowledge exchange, resource sharing, and interdisciplinary collaboration among researchers, practitioners, and industry stakeholders across Europe. Hence, we seek to overcome geographical barriers and create a seamless environment where expertise and resources can be accessed and utilized effectively. Furthermore, our objectives include promoting multi-dimensional research initiatives, encouraging the development of novel methodologies and tools, and facilitating the translation of research findings into real-world applications. Ultimately, we aim to position Europe at the forefront of research and innovation in edge AI systems, driving transformative impact and sustainable growth in the digital era.

However, such aim on collaborative and shared edge AI systems will require navigating through a series of legal and regulatory challenges. For instance, compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), particularly concerning the collection, processing, and storage of sensitive data from distributed sources, as well as compliance with the newly drafted EU AI Act. Additionally, clarifying ownership rights and establishing mechanisms for intellectual property protection, licensing, and commercialization presents challenges in cross-border collaborations. On the other hand, ethical considerations regarding AI governance, bias, transparency, and accountability must be addressed too, alongside with compliance with cybersecurity regulations and standards to safeguard sensitive data and infrastructure, e.g., NIS2 directive. Sector-specific regulations and

standards, such as medical device regulations and automotive safety standards, may also impact edge AI systems, necessitating ongoing and upcoming regulatory compliance efforts, e.g., EU AI Act. Moreover, determining liability and accountability in the event of errors or adverse outcomes requires clear contractual agreements and liability frameworks among the participants, i.e., members of this consortium and their corresponding partners who do not belong to the consortium.

2.3. Categorization of Edge AI Resources, Objects, Artifacts and Services

In this section, we discuss the classification strategy for organizing the inventory within the dAIEDGE consortium. Our classification methodology is inspired by the vision towards a robust architecture for the Virtual Center of Excellence (VoCE) and Virtual Research Labs (VLabs), which is expected to support the dynamic needs of highly distributed edge AI systems. Hence, the classification of the inventory is structured around three distinct layers, each serving a specific purpose within this architectural framework. As illustrated in Figure 1, at the core lies a foundational layer comprising edge AI services and objects, essential for driving innovation and research in edge AI computing. Surrounding this core is a middle layer dedicated to management and operational services, designed to streamline processes and to ensure the efficient functioning of the VoCE and VLabs. Finally, an outer layer is drawn to facilitate community-building services, fostering collaboration, knowledge sharing, and engagement among stakeholders.

2.3.1. Shell 1: Edge AI Core Services or Objects

The primary layer, Shell 1 of the classification framework, clusters the diverse array of edge AI services and objects available within the dAIEDGE consortium. It includes integral components such as edge AI models, datasets, computational facilities, and hardware infrastructure, which are essential in innovation and research in edge computing, e.g., edge AI hardware (edge computing platforms, robots, sensors, IoT devices, access points, etc.). We consider the following categories:

- Edge AI models, data, and software
 - edge AI models
 - software development and deployment pipelines (e.g. Bonseyes LPDNN tool and Benchmarking)
 - online testing tools
 - development pipelines (cloud-focus)
 - development pipelines (edge-focus)
 - software developer kits
 - datasets
- Cloud computing facilities for edge AI (e.g. from STM)

We anticipate that some of these assets/services will be made available in the VLab for the sharing of resources by partners in the MVP.

2.3.2. Shell 2: Management and operational services for dAIEDGE's virtual center

The secondary layer, the management and operational layer of the classification framework, encompasses a series of services that are essential for the efficient functioning of the Virtual Center of Excellence (VoCE) and Virtual Research Labs (VLabs). It includes key functionalities such as

authentication mechanisms, authorization mechanisms, compliance enforcement, and other operational services that will facilitate seamless collaboration and resource management within the dAIEDGE consortium. We consider the following categories:

- User authentication and authorization techniques, e.g., for remote access
- Technologies and concepts for enforcing legal compliance, e.g., GDPR
- Incentivization of the VLab usage (for both lab users and lab service providers), including IPR management and user incentive mechanisms.

2.3.3. Shell 3: Techniques and services for the community building by the virtual center

The tertiary/outer layer of the classification framework bundles the community-building services aimed at facilitating collaboration, knowledge sharing, and engagement among stakeholders of VoCE and VLabs. It includes initiatives such as AI marketplaces, software repositories, directories, and testbed federations, which will potentially serve to create a vibrant ecosystem of collaboration and innovation within the consortium. We consider the following categories:

- AI and edge AI software repositories
- edge AI software marketplaces,
- Testbed federations,
- Clearing houses, etc.

This layer could deliver connectivity of interoperability with the broader AI-on-Demand platform being built under the AI4Europe and Deploy AI projects.

3. Methods and Technologies

An inventory is generally a complete list or collection of items such as property, goods in stock, or a building's contents. For the dAIEDGE, an inventory is a continuously updated list or database of objects and services for distributed AI at the edge. A database entry typically lists the object type (incl. subtype), its name, where to find it, eventually the number of available items, who is responsible for the objects, and how one can use it.

Creating an inventory system from scratch is a challenging task. However, it is also one of the best ways to ensure that the dAIEDGE project can create a virtual center of excellence or the anticipated VLabs such that they are tailored to meet the specific dAIEDGE project aims.

In this section, we outline the methodology and concepts behind the creation of the inventory. We are focusing on the communication used to collect the information. This communication comprises the questionnaire, including its approach for using the above outlined ontology and categorization, and the ways and strategies that are used to interact and to communicate with the consortium for collecting the information. The section will detail the survey design, the communication and sampling strategy, the data collection process, and the measures taken to ensure the validity and reliability of the findings that will contribute to building an evolutive inventory of AI objects and services available in the dAIEDGE consortium.

3.1. Categorization of Edge AI Resources, Objects, Artifacts and Services

Deliverable D4.1 uses a survey-based approach as the primary method for data collection. However, a careful and verifiable design of the survey is required to obtain valid information for the inventory.

3.1.1. Why a questionnaire?

Task 4.1 uses a questionnaire as the primary method for data collection. A survey can easily reach all partners of dAIEDGE consortium and do this in a short time. Other and more target data collections methods, like interviews or example-driven ones (e.g. demonstrations or proof-of-concepts, cf. deliverable D6.1) might be also applicable. However, while they can obtain information in a well-controlled and focused way, these approaches typically require more time. In addition, an effort into a specific information gathering, e.g. an interview, might be easily wasted and void. For example, it turns out in an interview that a partner hasn't sufficient information. Hence, the comprehensiveness of the results by such dedicated collection activities is not guaranteed. Thus, the concept of questionnaire remains an appropriate collection method which can be well managed. Still, its limitations and challenges need to be highlighted and eventually overcome with other approaches.

3.1.2. Requirements

We expect that a large and newly formed consortium, like the one of dAIEDGE, needs to exchange large amounts of detailed technical information to facilitate collaboration, scientific and development aims.

Furthermore, one can expect that the partners are largely unknown to each other (this has been actually observed during the first months of the project). Thus, they need to establish a common syntax and a grammar, i.e. exchange and interpretation methods, to mutually exchange and to understand exchanged information.

It is likely that partners need to learn about this syntax and grammar. However, it takes time to establish productive data structures and interpretations of data. A communication concept should involve continuous updates and eventually repetitions. Furthermore, it should detail how information is exchanged, the identification of who is producing information, data about to whom should one send the information, or what are the required update mechanisms when new information becomes available, i.e., how to continually improve information quality.

Finally, while classifying edge AI objects is challenging, the novelty of the expected labs and of the center-of-excellence is probably founded in the context of using the contributed objects and services outside their typical use at the contributing partner. Hence, the questionnaire needs to ask also about those non-AI functions as well as the foundational and the context of AI functions. In addition, it needs to be expected that the responder of the questionnaire has a strong understanding of AI functions but not support functions for distributed AI.

3.1.3. Overall Design

The aim is to structure the questionnaire such that it systematically gathers information for the inventory. Hence, the focus is on the collection of technical information, i.e. on the edge AI objects

and services and which will be contributed by the consortium partners so that they can be embedded in the envisioned VLabs.

In addition, the foundations for creating new opportunities and unforeseen results by the VLabs and contributed objects need also to be addressed in the survey. Thus, the questionnaire is asking for additional information that enables the different context of using the resources. Such auxiliary information ranges from technical but non-typical edge AI services, e.g. user management, authentication, and authorization, to pure non-technical resources such as addition edge AI communities and how to connect to them.

Finally, the questionnaire is designed to provide means for a later refinement of the information of the inventory as well as for continuous updates of the inventory, see below.

3.1.4. Questions for Technical Information and for Context

As the inventory aims to provide a high inclusiveness of its entries, the applied categorization needs to correctly classify the AI objects. However, the ontology also needs to be general enough such that objects can be categorized by the responders that do not obviously fit into typical or object classes that are not yet foreseen. The latter is expected to increase the comprehensiveness of the inventory. Such a requirement might enable the inventory to list objects that are usually not visible.

The technical content of the questionnaire is structured with three distinct sets of clustered questions, strategically crafted to elicit comprehensive responses while allowing ample flexibility for diverse descriptions of inventory items. In addition to its primary purpose, our secondary objective is to delve into the challenges and context inherent in establishing a virtual lab environment to foster seamless cooperation and collaboration among stakeholders. By addressing these challenges head-on, we aim to gain valuable insights that will help within the development of effective strategies and solutions to enhance the collaborative potential of the virtual lab. The clusters are:

- Shell 1: Edge AI core services or objects
- Shell 2: Management and operational services for dAIEDGE's virtual center, including context.
- Shell 3: Techniques and services for the community building by the virtual center, including context.

3.1.5. Questions and Answers for Continuous and Refined Information Collection

Furthermore, the questionnaire aims at continuous and refined information collection. Hence, it starts with identifying the institution and the person (incl. email) who is providing the information. This approach enables the collectors to re-check with distinct people at the partners, e.g., for refining information.

In addition, the survey provides the specific option "later" as an answer for the responder. This option should be chosen if the answering person has not currently sufficient information to answer but expects that this information will be available. This answer also allows the data collection team to analyze the responses and to understand whether more information is available and can be

eventually requested. Thus, options might lead to targeted and continuous refinements and updates of the inventory.

3.2. Microsoft Forms as a Tool

Despite many survey tools being available, like SurveyMonkey (surveyMonkey.com), Google Forms (docs.google.com/forms), or FillOut (fillout.com), we decided to use the well-known Microsoft Forms (<https://forms.microsoft.com/>) as the tool for this survey.

Microsoft Forms is a well-known online survey creator, part of Office 365 and released in June 2016. It allows data collectors to create surveys and quizzes quickly and efficiently with automatic marking and responses. Responders can also rapidly respond, and they can make use of their experiences with the common look and feel of Microsoft products. In addition, the data can be easily exported to Microsoft Excel.

We have chosen Forms because of its simplicity of use in terms of providing information. We expect most dAIEDGE partners are focused on edge AI activities and are not willing to spend a long time in front of a survey tool. Forms is part of Office 365 and thus most users are experienced with its look, feel, and straightforward usage.

However, it should be mentioned that Microsoft Form imposes challenges in creating surveys due to its limitation in questions being context-aware of answers and the strict design constraint, probably to maintain the rendering and tool of questionnaires easy.

3.3. Information Collection and Information Compilation

dAIEDGE is a consortium of highly excellent partners with an outstanding variety of skills. However, many consortium partners have not been collaborating before. Hence, they need an understanding on how to interact on core edge AI artifacts in the framework of a virtual center. At first, they need to understand why and how to contribute the required information to the inventory.

3.3.1. Strategy

Hence, the task developed a two-phase strategy for information and collection and compilation. In phase 1, an initial inventory is established. The partners are guided-at-large to provide the information. This includes coaching on the importance and nature of the virtual centers and support on filling the questionnaire. At the end of phase 1, the very first gap analysis will be given.

Phase 2 aims at a refinement of the inventory. The quality of the information in the inventory should be verified and eventually be enhanced. In addition, the comprehensiveness of the inventory should be improved, e.g., target key players to provide information. Phase 2 will start with a deeper analysis of the inventory and will increase the interaction with task 4.1.

Next, we detail the activities foreseen for information collection and building the inventory during the two phases.

3.3.2. Phase 1 (Creation of the Inventory):

Phase 1 describes the activities for an initial inventory, i.e. for the M06 version of D4.1. We will also provide a timeline for the activities to be conducted during the first six months of the task. These activities comprise:

- Planning of the timeline to establish the inventory
- Refinement of the initial vision for the virtual center-of-excellence and for the VLabs
- Development of an ontology and categorization scheme for distributed AI edge objects and services
- Create a questionnaire, based on the ontology, that can rapidly be comprehended and answered by the responders.
- Coaching and updating the responders about the aims of the inventory and the timeline for providing the information.
- Distribution of the questionnaire within the consortium and reminders for filling the questionnaire.
- Supporting the responders with multiple “Questions & Answer” sessions; the sessions allow for individual questions about filling in the required information.
- Coordination within the task about continuous refinement and updates to the inventory.
- Make use of the project coordinator and his capability to distribute information and motivate partners to participate in the survey.
- Design a questionnaire where information can be related to partners and to contact persons who can response to questions about refinement.

These activities are scheduled as given in Table 1. The table shows the time when action should be completed (in weeks before the due date of the M06 version of the deliverable D4.2 as well as the action involved and the responsible partner). (*) Remark: the activities start two months after the start of the project, since they rely on communication capabilities within dAIEDGE, like mailing lists, which need to be established first.

Table 2: Schedule of the Activities in Phase 2: Creating the Inventory

Time before due date	Actions	Responsible Role or Partner
16 weeks (*)	Start-up of the task, coordination with the WP leader	WP leader, task leader
12 weeks	Developing a feasible schedule for collecting and creating the M06 version of the inventory	task leader
10 weeks	Initial vision for the virtual center-of-excellence and for the VLabs Development of an ontology/categorization for distributed AI edge objects and services Identification of tools for the questionnaire	task leader

8 weeks	Creation of questionnaire based on ontology. Early information to the responders about the aims of the inventory and the timeline for providing the information	task leader
6 weeks	Distribution of the questionnaire within the consortium	task leader
5 weeks	Reminder for filling the questionnaire First "Questions & Answer" session	task leader
4 weeks	Reminder for filling the questionnaire by the project leadership First "Questions & Answer" session	Project coordinator, task leader
3 weeks	Coordination with other participants in the task about future activities and continuous refinements of the inventory Definition of table of content of deliverable and start of writing First "Questions & Answer" session	task leader, task member
2 weeks	Creation of the first version of the inventory and initial gap analysis Submission of deliverable for internal review	task leader
1 week	Internal review and addressing the internal review comment	review team, task leader
Due date	Finalization and submission of deliverable	task leader

3.3.3. Phase 2 (Improving the Quality):

Phase 2 will focus on refining the comprehensiveness of the inventory, improving the information quality in the inventory, and on the enhancement and verification of the categorization needs to describe the entries into the inventory.

Phase 2 aims at a deeper integration with task T4.2, who should be a primary consumer of the information available in the inventory. (**) Remark: Task T4.2 is just starting at the time of writing this deliverable.

Table2: Schedule of the Activities in Phase 2: Improving the Quality

Time before due date	Actions	Responsible Role or Partner
24 weeks (**)	Presentation of the first result to the consortium and to T4.2. Collection of input from partner, particular larger partners.	WP leader, task leader, task participants, consortium

22 weeks	<p>Startup of regular synchronization within WP4 and particular with WP4 and between tasks T4.1 and T4.2</p> <p>Improved gap analysis based on available information and improved time planning.</p> <p>Definition of detailed refinement strategy for the inventory (e.g. focus on missing partners and/or licensing issues) and the categorization scheme, considering the needs of T4.2</p>	WP4 leader, task leader T4.1, task leader T4.2, T4.1 participants
18 weeks	<p>First round of information collection from key partners completed.</p> <p>First round of synchronization with T4.2</p> <p>Verification of database structure for inventory</p>	task leader T4.1, T4.1 participants, task leader T4.2
14 weeks	<p>Second round of information collection from key partners completed.</p> <p>Second round of synchronization with T4.2</p> <p>Update of database structure for inventory (if needed)</p>	task leader T4.1, T4.1 participants, task leader T4.2
10 weeks	<p>Third round information collection from key partners completed (if needed)</p> <p>Third round of synchronization with T4.2</p> <p>Controlling the inventory quality</p>	task leader T4.1, T4.1 participants, task leader T4.2
6 weeks	<p>Definition of a table of content of the M12 version of the deliverable D4.1 and start of writing of the final D.4.1</p> <p>Defining a sustainability plan for the inventory</p>	task leader T4.1, T4.1 participants, task leader T4.2
4 weeks	Internal progress evaluation of the D4.1 (incl. inventory content)	task leader T4.1, T4.1 participants
2 weeks	Finalization and submission of deliverable for internal review	task leader T4.1, T4.1 participants,
1 week	Internal review and addressing the internal review comment	review team, task leader T4.1, T4.1 participants
Due date	Finalization and submission of deliverable	task leader T4.1

3.4. The Inventory

The inventory is currently an Excel file and uses the typical XML format for Microsoft documents. It contains the raw output of the responses to the questionnaire as entered by dAIEDGE partners and generated by the Microsoft Form. The use of Excel is justified by ease of use and maintainance, the simple data structure, and efficiently storage of the file in the MS Teams server of the dAIEDGE project. The M06 version of the inventory is available as an Excel File (“Evolutive_Infrastructure_Inventory_M06.xlsx”) upon request.

However, it should be noted that the inventory should enable more complex queries on its data, e.g. “show all partners that have AI models of a specific class”. Such queries can probably not easily be done within an Excel file and a real database (incl. a database and query management system, DBMS), might be needed. However, such more complex queries are currently not yet defined. Hence, we think that an Excel-based solution is currently a good choice.

3.4.1. Format of the Excel File of the Inventory

Next, we describe the format and semantics of the columns and rows in Excel file of the inventory.

Columns: The first two columns in the Excel file show the start and completion time for the questionnaire. Columns D, E, and F are redundant ones. They are the result of Microsoft Teams creating the Excel file.

For the remaining columns starting from G, each column corresponds to a specific question in the survey and in a sequential manner. Table 3 specifies which questions in the survey are related to which specific column in Excel. The questions are given in the screenshot in Annex A.

Table 3: Question number to Excel column mapping

Question Number in the Questionnaire	Figure No (Annex A)	Column in Excel
1	III	G
2	III	H
3	III	I
4	IV	J
5	IV	K
6	V	L
7	V	M
8	V	N
9	VI	O
10	VI	P
11	VII	Q
12	VII	R
13	VII	S
14	VIII	T
15	VIII	U
16	IX	V
17	IX	W

18	IX	X
19	X	Y

Rows: Each row of the Excel files corresponds to an individual response from one partner. We are currently not allowing multiple rows for the same partner. This requirement has been imposed for being quickly able to understand which dAIEDGE members have responded to and to avoid multiple entries for the same resource. Furthermore, the single entry for each partner is transferred in an automatic way into the Excel file by MS Forms. This approach avoids any data loss due to the collector the interpretation and transfer from an “answers per partner” into an “answer-per-object”.

A sorting and distinction by rows for individual objects might also be desirable. However, this requires probably an unambiguous identification of objects and, in turn, an almost finalized categorization. Such a categorization, however, is not yet available and needs to be synchronized with T4.2.

4. Results and First Gap Analysis

Next, we present some selected results and content from the survey and the inventory. This should highlight what kind of information is or will be in the inventory. In order to increase the information quality of the inventory, we provide also a first gap analysis.

4.1. Overview on Data Collection and Answering Partners

The survey was sent to the general dAIEDGE mailing lists (all@daiedge.eu, wp4@daiedge.eu) on 15th January 2024 and we asked the consortium to reply by 31st January 2024. As of now (date: Feb 15, 2024), there are a total of 35 active partners in the project. A total of 26 valid responses were received from 23 partner institutions, a 66% response rate. In addition, there were a few multiple entries from the same partners. However, the questionnaire remains open.

It should be noted that the median of the time taken by a responder to answer the questionnaire was 28 minutes. In our opinion, this value indicates that the answering partners were careful and took sufficient time to answer the questionnaire. This time duration is in the range of the duration of what was expected to answer the survey, assuming that most of the partners are new to the concept of a virtual center of excellence and the VLabs.

In addition, not all consortium partners have worktime (person months, PMs) allocated in this task and yet they were asked to contribute.

All in all, it can be concluded that the questionnaire had a high response ratio (66%) from all partners. However, a closer look on the missing responses reveals that some very large and commercially focused partners have not answered yet. Furthermore, also some large research focused partners are missing. The reasons for the missing answers are up for further investigations and will be discussed within the consortium. A list of answering partners and contact points is available on request from the T4.1 task leader due to privacy requirements.

4.2. Overview on Inventory Content

We now provide an overview on the content of inventory and will highlight remarkable observations that we made when doing a first analysis of the inventory. The presentation of the content follows the categorization according to the shell as introduced in Section 2.3.

4.2.1. Shell 1: Edge AI Core Services or Objects

The inventory currently contains more than 20 software objects, 13 hardware object types, and two Cloud facilities.

Software: Diving further into the subcategories, the software catalog is split into 16 edge AI models, nine software pipelines, eight datasets, and a few other development pipelines and software kits. Additional contributions include collaborative, privacy-preserving computation frameworks, and benchmarks. A brief list of core AI Edge software examples is given below.

Hardware: We observe that many current and future AI hardware platforms for edge or embedded computing are contributed such as MP SoC, Nvidia Jetsons, etc. However, only a few application-oriented edge devices like VR headsets are available. A brief list of core AI Edge hardware examples is given below.

Information quality for Shell 1: 19 members listed at least one contribution to the inventory, and seven members' responses mentioned that their contributions is “none” or will be updated later. Only 13 responses provided URL links for documentation or references and the remaining 13 responses provided a short description of the AI services. When asked about potential future contributions to the inventory list, 15 members responded with “Later”, 4 members responded with “None”, and only 7 members were able to provide an answer.

List of Core AI Edge Hardware Examples:

- Evaluation boards for edge AI open-source platforms (PULP chips) incl. development
- Open-source RISC-V-based systems for AI applications (<https://www.pulp-platform.org>)
- MPSoC (FPGA+ARM) hardware platform
- AR-helmet (Edge AI Hardware), AR-compute-unit (Edge AI Hardware) (www.aegisrider.com)
- Varjo XR-3 headsets
- Development kits for various edge hardware: RBPi-4B, Nvidia Xavier, Nvidia Jetson nano, Nvidia Jetson Orin, (<https://beta.bonseyes.com/>)
- Neuromorphic computing platform: automated model-to-VHDL generation for any arbitrary spiking neural network (edge AI hardware)
- EDA Knowledge and experience, Hardware power estimation

List of Core AI Edge Software Examples:

- MPSoC (FPGA+ARM) Xilinx development pipeline
- Multi-Task Learning models aimed at edge computing from AI Witchlabs (: <https://ai-benchmark.com/ranking.html>)
- AR-rider (dataset), AR-cloud (training and deployment pipeline) (www.aegisrider.com)

- GATE benchmarking suite for broader ML models, adaptably for edge cases),
- TALI, a full multimodal model for robust cross-modal model development (<https://github.com/AntreasAntoniou/GATE>),
- BMP (Bonseyes AI Marketplace), LPDNN (Low Power Deep Neural Network Framework), DPE (Developer Platform Environments) (<https://beta.bonseyes.com/>)
- HSTP (Hyperspace Transaction Protocol), HSML (Hyperspace Modeling Language), Active Inference Models, <https://www.verses.ai/>,
- Test beds compilation, Machine Learning models deployment, Virtual Research Lab implementation, Middleware implementation (<https://bisite.usal.es/en/research/projects/nationals?page=1>)
- DMWay (Middleware for IoT infrastructure integration), TRAIL & Cyberexcellence Factories (AI and security software factories) (TrailFactory (<https://factory.trail.ac/>), (<https://factory.cyberexcellence.be/>), DMWay (<https://asset.cetic.be/en/dmway/>))

4.2.2. Shell 2: Management and Operational Services

The responses for the part of the survey on management and operation services were rather limited. For example, eight partners answered with “later” when asked about mechanisms for authorization and authentication for the remote usage and the access management of contributed core AI objects. However, at least 13 members described at least one mechanism. Thus, we conclude that authorization and authentication mechanisms are often available, but responders are often not aware of them.

A similar pattern can be observed when the partners are asked about technologies and concepts to enforce legal compliance IPR management, or GDPR. Here, twelve members responded with “later”, and one member responded with “I don’t know, but we use one”. The remaining thirteen responses mentioned software licensing, GDPR compliance of data, Data protection officer, and opensource licenses.

When asked about potential for incentivizing the usage of VLabs, twelve members responded with “not needed”, three responded with “I don’t know”, two responded with “Later”, and three responded with “not clear at the moment”. However, six members saw the potential of incentivizing the VLabs and made suggestions such as:

- “For users, remote access to specialized equipment, flexible scheduling and reduced travel costs are significant benefits. On the other hand, providers can adopt flexible business models, ensure quality and security, integrate with educational platforms and offer efficient technical support. In terms of payment mechanisms, options such as pay-per-use, monthly subscriptions and freemium models”
- “Can develop incentive mechanisms such as points, badges, for usage and user contributions. These could be framed as tokenized incentives to be recorded on a blockchain or hashed.”
- “As far as lab service providers go, I do not think the major problem is on the incentive side, but on the barriers (who are intended platform users, what data they are going to bring to the platform etc.). As far as lab users go, I think the major incentive is the cost factor: If they have

access to cheaper devices than what the cloud provides, most probably they will use the platform”

4.2.3. Shell 3: Techniques and Services for Community Building

For the questions related to which software repository is used by the partners, the vast majority answered (18 out of 23) GitLab. This underlines the importance of this repository tool. We expect that the virtual centers of dAIEDGE will need to include it deeply into the design, research, and engineering workflows in the VLabs.

Other examples for mechanisms and services for community building are:

- “Newsletters”
- “TRAIL & Cyberexcellence Factories services (Git Repository, software repository, marketplace, newsletter, LinkedIn, workshops)”
- “Bonseyes AI Marketplace”
- “Scientific publications, conference/workshop presentations, social media, webinars, workshops”
- “Organization of the public tinyML Challenge 2023 and 2024.”
- “Organizing workshops on Benchmarking for Edge AI each year”

Finally, we observed a rather large number of answers to the question which other stakeholders and infrastructures outside the dAIEDGE consortium should be included into the virtual center of excellence. Here some of these answers:

- “Use the Vlab as a testing and experimentation facility integrated with the Bonseyes Marketplace and the AI-on-Demand platform”
- “Test beds federation <https://www.fed4fire.eu/testbeds/>”
- “dAIEDGE should include other stakeholders such as more companies for the testing of everything that can be developed during the project and entities that can certify compliance with the European AI standards set by the EU.”
- “AI4Europe, DeployAI (CSA for AioD), Rebecca, EdgeAI, ICT-48 RIAs and CSA, ICT-49 Ias, Claire, Ellis, BDVA (www.bdva.eu), ECSEL joined undertaking (www.ecsel.eu), Fed4FIRE (<http://www.fed4fire.eu/testbeds/>) is a federation of 24 testbeds spread over Europe, OneLab (<https://onelab.eu/>) an experimental facility made up of a federation of future Internet testbeds, IoT lab (<http://www.iotlab.eu/>) federates several IoT testbeds.”
- “The AI Witchlabs benchmark for mobile phone AI readiness”

4.3. First Gap Analysis

While the questionnaire resulted in a good response rate of about 66% (23 out of 35), only one third of the partners provided an answer. Thus, one can conclude the inventory is yet less comprehensive. In addition, it is obvious that certain large and commercially focused partners have not yet answered. As similar observation holds for a couple of large research focused partners. The reason is yet unknown and a detailed investigation on their reasons should be carried out, e.g. asking the these partners specifically about the roadblocks for not answering and providing support to resolve

them. A current hypothesis for this is that these partners may offer a very large variety of services and objects. They might have many contact points and it requires time for them to catalog and list them. Furthermore, the commercial nature of such object might incur licensing issues, which needs to be addressed and solved.

Nevertheless, more than 33 types of core edge AI hardware and software objects and services have been entered into the directory. We observe that many edge or embedded computing platforms seem to be accessible, but only a few end-user devices, such as VR headsets are offered for sharing. For example, access to robots was not given.

Another gap might be the limited understanding by partner on requirements for “Management and Operational” for the virtual centers. Here, only a few answers were given. The concepts and techniques provided by ETSI’s NFV Open-Source MANO framework should eventually be considered here (<https://www.etsi.org/technologies/open-source-mano>). Most of the responses in this shell focused on the primary requirement of the authentication and authorization of users within the VLabs.

It is remarkable for shell 3 that we can observe a large willingness and engagement of partners into community building. An important requirement here is maintaining or relating to GitHub as an important tool for collaboration. This tool is very well known and used by the vast majority of users. However, additional concepts are welcome and should complete this, including software marketplaces. It is probably very productive for the dAIEDGE partners to name stakeholders and infrastructures that should be included in the VLabs. Thus partners could be: “AI4Europe, DeployAI (CSA for AIoD), Rebecca, ICT-48 RIAs and CSA, ICT-49 IAs, Claire, Ellis, BDVA (www.bdva.eu), ECSEL joined undertaking (www.ecsel.eu), OneLab (<https://onelab.eu/>), IoT lab (<http://www.iotlab.eu/>), or Fed4FIRE (<http://www.fed4fire.eu/testbeds/>). This information should probably be handed over to T4.2 for the virtual center design and a plan or technologies to engage them could be designed.

Finally, the inventory is currently a simple Excel file which is available to all partners within the dAIEDGE MS Teams. The inventory should be transferred into a real database, such that more complex queries can be used for searching for resources, and the inventory can also the role of a “clearing house” which can control and orchestrate resource usage.

5. Summary and Conclusion

This deliverable provides the first and not yet comprehensive inventory of edge AI objects available in the dAIEDGE consortium and potentially available for inclusion in the foreseen virtual center of excellence and VLabs to be designed within the project. An evolution of the inventory will be available at M12 (month 12) of the project.

This M06 version of the Evolutive Infrastructure Inventory (Report Nr 1, Deliverable D4.1) aims at a concise and structured survey for obtaining the content of the inventory, i.e. the information about hardware and software objects for distributed AI at the edge. The document aims to provide verifiable information on how the survey was structured and what kind of categorization was

applied. The categorization was assuming a first vision for the virtual centers. The vision has been outlined in this document.

The inventory reveals that a large variety of objects is available. These objects comprise more than 20 kinds of software object and about 10-15 hardware types. The survey obtained a sufficient ratio (66%) of dAIEDGE partners who have responded to the survey. However, it became obvious that larger partners, who are expected to contribute numerous hardware and software objects, have not fully yet replied. A more fine-grained analysis of this miss needs to be carried out. A hypothesis for this reason is the complexity of these partners. They might have many contact points within their institutions for these assets and the contribution might encounter legal issues, e.g. licensing requirements. We expect that these partners need dedicated support, and we will adapt our inventory gathering strategy accordingly for the next version of the inventory. Another observed and well received effect is that this deliverable sparked discussion with task T4.1 and task 7.1 (Benchmarks for micro, deep and meta Edge AI) about available benchmark concepts.

Finally, a significant improvement of the inventory is expected for the M12 version of the inventory. A time plan and a plan for measures for improving the inventory has been suggested in this document.

The M06 version of the inventory is available as an Excel File ("Evolutive_Infrastructure_Inventory_M06.xlsx") upon request.

ANNEX A: Questionnaire for filling the Inventory.

The questionnaire used for the inventory is documented below. It consists of nine sections which are organized into two main parts. The first part comprises sections 1-5. They provide instructions, motivation, and a technical vision for the virtual center of excellence, categorization of objects, and request partner information. The sections are shown in Figures (I, II, and III).

The second part consists of the remaining four sections (6-9). Section 6 consists of 5 questions on Shell 1 (Core AI services and Objects), shown in Figures (IV, V). Section 7 focuses on Shell 2 (Resource management and operational service), and it also has 5 questions, shown in Figures (VI, VII). Section 8 has 5 questions on Shell 3 (Resources for community building) and is shown in Figures (VIII, IX, X). Finally, section 9 consists of the final message and contact details for any queries on filling out the questionnaire, shown in Figure (XI).

The screenshot displays a questionnaire interface with three sections, each in a light blue box with a title and a three-dot menu icon in the top right corner.

Section 1

dAIEDGE's Objective 5 on "Building a Connected Virtual Centre of Excellence for edge AI"

Section 2

Instructions

Please fill in the questionnaire with information about resources you, as a partner, might contribute or would like to see included in shells of the integration model! However, please read our description and motivation first!

Section 3

Motivation

dAIEDGE aims at building a virtual center of excellence. The target is accelerating and deepening Europe's edge AI research and commercialization. The center will be one or more virtual environments for expedited research and development of cutting-edge technologies and business opportunities for edge AI applications, technologies, and systems.

In addition, the center will be a place for community building and collaborations with other relevant and excellent stakeholders outside the consortium. We aim to include in the center future players like Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH), AI start-up initiatives, incubators, international industrial and scientific clusters, etc.

The virtual centre will be implemented by designing a framework for edge AI resource integration and by building one or more virtual laboratory environments (vlabs). The vlabs will be characterized by high usability, simple accessibility, efficient interoperability, and appropriate security, compliance, and incentivization mechanisms.

The virtual labs (vlabs) will integrate the vast number of cutting-edge AI technologies and resources available within the consortium. They will provide access to these resources to all partners and, if possible, beyond.

We hope the labs will become venues for advanced research activities and business development previously impossible for individual consortium partners. For example, the vlabs should permit testing edge AI models in environments not available at a partner's location.

Figure I - Questionnaire – Instructions and motivation

Technical Vision for the Virtual Centre of Excellence:

Figure 1: dAledge AI-as-a-Service vision

dAledge’s vision for an integration framework can be visualized by a three-layer onion model, cf. Figure 1. The model outlines some of the layers’ functions and their relationships among their level of hierarchy. The dAledge model comprises currently three shells:

- a) Shell1: edge AI core services or objects:
 - edge AI hardware (edge computing platforms, robots, sensors, IoT devices, access points, etc.)
 - edge AI models, data, and software
 - i. edge AI models
 - ii. software development and deployment pipelines (e.g. Boneyes LPDNN) tool
 - iii. online testing tools
 - iv. development pipelines (cloud-focus)
 - v. development pipelines (edge-focus)
 - vi. software developer kit
 - vii. data sets
 - Cloud computing facilities for edge AI (e.g. STM’s ...)
 - User authentication and authorization techniques, e.g. for remote access
 - Technologies and concepts for enforcing legal compliance, e.g. GDPR, or software license concept (incl. opensource ones) for IPR management
 - Incentivization of the vlab usage (for both, lab users and lab service providers), incl. payment mechanisms (if applicable)
- b) Shell 2: Management and operational services for dAledge’s virtual centre
 - User authentication and authorization techniques, e.g. for remote access
 - Technologies and concepts for enforcing legal compliance, e.g. GDPR, or software license concept (incl. opensource ones) for IPR management
 - Incentivization of the vlab usage (for both, lab users and lab service providers), incl. payment mechanisms (if applicable)
- c) Shell 3: Techniques and services for the community building by the virtual centre:
 - AI and edge AI software repositories
 - edge AI software marketplaces,
 - Testbed federations,
 - Clearing houses, etc.
 - Other relevant stakeholders that need to be included
 - Other relevant infrastructures from outside partners that need to be included

Figure II - Questionnaire – Technical vision for virtual centre of excellence

Section 5 ...

Partner Information

1
Please enter your partner institution name *

Enter your answer

2
Please enter your name (i.e. the name of who is entering the information or who can be contact for further information) *

Enter your answer

3
Please enter your email address (for being contacted) *

Enter your answer

Figure III - Questionnaire Section 5 – contact point details page (Q No. 1,2,3)

Section 6

...

Shell 1 resources: edge AI core services or objects

4

What types edge AI core services and objects can your institution contribute to vlabs? *

- edge AI hardware (edge computing platforms, robots, sensors, IoT devices, access points, etc.)
- edge AI models, data, and software
- Cloud computing facilities for edge AI (e.g. STM's edge AI)

...

5

What kind of subcategories are applicable for contributed software objects *

- Edge AI models
- Software development and deployment pipelines (e.g. Boneyes LPDNN)
- Development pipelines (cloud-focus)
- Development pipelines (edge focused)
- Software developer kits
- Data sets
- Other

Figure IV - Questionnaire Section 6 – Shell 1 Core AI services and objects Part –1 (Q No. 4,5)

6

Please list and describe the edge AI core services and objects that can be contributed by your institution.

- Please use a new line for each resource or object that will be contributed
- Add one or more attributes (see above) for each resource or object
- Entry example entries (longer entries are welcome):
 - BTH-VR-data (data set)
 - LPDNN (deployment pipeline)
- Please enter "none" if your institution can't contribute any resources.
- Please enter "later" if you can't name the resources at the moment.

*

Enter your answer

⋮

7

Please enter URLs or other references for documentation for the contributed edge AI core services, objects, and resources!

- Entry example entries:
 - BTH-VR-data (www.bth.se)
- Please enter "none" if your institution can't contribute any resources.
- Please enter "later" if you can't name the resources at the moment.

*

Enter your answer

8

Could you forecast the development of edge AI core objects and services that could be added to the inventory of dAledge in the near future?

- Please enter "none" if you don't see additional needs.
- Please enter "later" if you can't name or forecast the resources.

*

Enter your answer

Figure V - Questionnaire Section 6 – Shell 1 Core AI services and objects part-1 (Q. No. 6,7,8)

Shell 2 resource: management and operational services and objects the for virtual centre

9

Please describe the user authentication and authorization techniques, e.g., for remote access, that are used by your institution for usage/access management of core edge AI resources!

- Examples:
 - local solution
 - OpenID
 - LDAP, RADIUS, Kerberos
 - even: "I don't know, but we use one."
 - or: "no, we don't use authorization techniques"
- Please write text or give examples.
- Please enter "later" if you can't provide information at the moment.

*

Enter your answer

10

Please briefly elaborate on the technologies and concepts used by your institution for enforcing legal compliance, e.g. GDPR, or software license concepts (incl. open-source ones) for IPR management.

- Please write text.
- Please enter "later" if you can't provide information at the moment.
- Please enter "compliance not needed" if you don't see any potential or need for compliance enforcement
- Please enter "licences not needed" if you don't see any potential or need for software licences

*

Enter your answer

Figure VI - Questionnaire Section 7 – Shell 2 Resource management and operational service Part-1 (Q. No. 9, 10)

11

Please provide a forecast on the potential to incentivize of vlab usage (for both lab users and lab service providers), including payment mechanisms (if applicable).

- Please write text.
- Please enter "not needed" if you don't see any potential or need for incentivizing the contribution of resources.

*

Enter your answer

12

Could you forecast the development of operational services for the user, compliance, incentivization, and license management in dAledge in the near future?

- Please write text.
- Please enter "none" if you don't see additional needs.
- Please enter "later" if you can't name or forecast the service.

*

Management and operational services

Enter your answer

⋮

13

Can your institution contribute to the management and operation of service of the vlabs?

Please name the services your institution can contribute to the management and operation. Please provide URLs or other references to any documentation.

- Entry example entries:
 - BonsApps ORDL model for license management (BonsApps deliverable D3.4; www.bonsapps.eu)
- Please enter "none" if your institution can't contribute.
- Please enter "later" if you can't name the service or find the documentation at the moment.

*

Enter your answer

Figure VII - Questionnaire Section 7 – Shell 2 Resource management and operational service Part-2 (Q. No. 11, 12,13)

Section 8

...

Shell 3 resources: techniques/services for community building

14

Currently, which services or techniques are used by your institution for community building

- AI and edge AI software repositories
- Edge AI software marketplaces
- GIT repository
- Test-bed federation facility
- Clearing houses, etc.
- Other

15

Please name the services or techniques your institution **currently** is using for community building.

- Please use a new line for each service or technique
- Please enter "none" if your institution doesn't use community building.
- Please enter "later" if you can name the services or techniques now.

*

Figure VIII - Questionnaire Section 8 – Shell 3 Community building Part-1 (Q. No. 14, 15)

16

In the future: which services or techniques would your institution like to use for community building?

- AI and edge AI software repositories
- Edge AI software marketplaces
- GIT respository
- Test-bed federation facility
- Clearing houses, etc.
- Other

17

Please name specific services or techniques your institution would like to use for community building **in the future.**

- Please use a new line for each service or technique (if possible, provide URLs)
- Please enter "none" if your institution doesn't want to use community building.
- Please enter "later" if you can't name the services or techniques now.

*

Enter your answer

⋮

18

Which other relevant stakeholders does dAledge need to include for community management?

- Please use a new line for each stakeholder (if possible, provide URLs)
- Please enter "none" if your institution doesn't want other community management stakeholders.
- Please enter "later" if you can't name the stakeholder.

*

Enter your answer

Figure IX - Questionnaire Section 8 – Shell 3 Community building Part-2 (Q. No. 16, 17, 18)

19

Finally, which other relevant infrastructure from outside partners must be included in the vlabs or the dAledge virtual centre?

- Please use a new line for each infrastructure (if possible, provide URLs)
- Please enter "none" if your institution doesn't see any further needs.
- Please enter "later" if you can't name the infrastructure.

*

Enter your answer

Figure X - Questionnaire Section 8 – Shell 3 Community building Part-3 (Q. No. 19)

Section 9

Thanks a lot for providing the answers. Your support is very appreciated!

Please get in touch with nurul.momen@bth.se for further questions.

Have a great day!

Your T4.1 team

Figure XI - Questionnaire Section 9 – Support page

daiedge.eu